

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MARKETING IN COMBATING UNSUSTAINABLE CONSUMER BEHAVIOR AND FOOD WASTE

Manuela APETREI^{1*}, Ioan SURDU¹, Carmen CĂTUNĂ BOCA¹

¹ Centre for Mountain Economy “CE-MONT” of the National Institute for Economic Research “Costin C. Kirițescu” - INCE, Romanian Academy, Str. Petreni, no. 49, Vatra Dornei, Romania

*Corresponding author: sincari_manuela@yahoo.com

Abstract

Food waste has become a major challenge both nationally and internationally. The constant promotion of abundance in the consumer society, combined with the cheapening of products and services, has generated the emergence of wasteful behavior. This trend can only be changed by educating and making people aware of the consequences of their actions and the benefits of redistributing, recycling or donating products, guided by the principles of ethical consumption. Preventing waste involves steps aimed at educating consumers on the one hand, and optimizing agricultural systems responsible for providing food on the other. Preventing food waste can only be achieved through a joint global effort, requiring consumer involvement, political will, propaganda, and understanding public policy instruments. The involvement of society and governments can also be achieved with the help of social marketing. Social marketing proves to be extremely useful in carrying out efforts to promote social causes, in our case the reduction of food waste through rational and sustainable consumption. Social marketing techniques are used to disseminate messages to different target groups. These messages aim to raise awareness of a specific behavior and are adapted according to the characteristics of the target group (age, socio-economic status). The final objective of the message transmitted with the help of social marketing is to mobilize, empower or inform the target audience. Basically, education is what produces awareness of the problems and this gives rise to a change in mentality, attitude and behavior, generating accountability.

Keywords: food waste, social marketing, consumer behavior, consumerism, rational consumption

INTRODUCTION

Food waste phenomenon is a challenge both at the national and international level. Food waste affects biodiversity, generates pollution and involves the consumption of a significant amount of raw materials (European Commission 2019: 11). For this reason, combating the phenomenon of food waste is crucial for sustainable development.

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) gave the following definition of food waste: *food and associated inedible parts removed from the human food supply chain in the following sectors: manufacturing of food products (under certain circumstances); food/grocery retail; food service and households* (United Nations Environment Programme 2021: 19).

The growing need for good quality, healthy and affordable food requires a multi- and transdisciplinary approach (United Nations 2015). It is also desired by the year 2030, to reduce by 50% the phenomenon of food waste, mainly in the phase of retail sale as well as in that of consumption (Gorgan et al. 2022), according to objective 12.3 within the 17 objectives of sustainable development of the United Nations (Djekic et al. 2021; Schinkel 2019), the solution coming from increasing consumer awareness.

The prevention of waste involves actions that have as their goal the education of the consumer on the one hand, and on the other hand the optimization of the agricultural systems responsible for the supply of food products. Both the reduction of food waste (Gkountani & Tsoulfas 2021) and the circular economy (Adelodun et al. 2021) contribute to the sustainability of the food system, the latter being based on local production.

A peculiarity regarding to food waste is found in the mountainous area in the countryside, because in this area, the phenomenon has relatively small dimensions due to the fact that the resulting remains are taken up in the animal circuit (the animals that make up the small household in the mountain area). Moreover, the small household in the mountain area also requires the existence of a garden in which potatoes, onions, carrots, beets, etc. are grown, crops resistant to the mountain climatic peculiarities. These products, once grown, are stored in appropriate conditions (in this case cellars or pantries), and everything that is unfit for human consumption ends up being consumed by the animals of the mountain household (Antonescu et al. 2023; Rey 1979).

The permanent promotion of abundance in the consumer society, combined with the cheapening of products and services, has generated the appearance of wasteful behavior.

When we talk about food waste, we must also consider the costs associated with this phenomenon: economic costs and environmental costs. Economic costs include the costs of the products themselves as well as the costs associated with the production, transport and storage of wasted products. Environmental costs are related to the increase in greenhouse gas emissions, but also the costs associated with wasted resources: water, energy.

The specific causes of food waste (Fig. 1) vary from country to country around the world and depend very much on the specific conditions combined with the level of education in that country. The causes of food waste have been recognized and analyzed by several authors from the specialized literature (Amicarelli et al. 2021; Chauhan et al. 2021; Do et al. 2021; Evans 2011; FAO 2011; Girotto et al. 2015; Priefer 2016).

Fig. 1: Causes of food waste

Source: the authors

Moreover, the causes of food waste differ from developed to developing countries, with the greatest waste in developing countries occurring at the early stage, after harvesting and processing, while in developed countries, waste occurs at the retail stage and at the consumption stage.

The diversity and complexity of the causes that generate food waste require specific monitoring systems on all links of the food chain (Ocicka & Raźniewska 2018), as well as a detailed analysis to effectively outline the reduction, informational, regulatory and cultural policies.

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

From the perspective of the methodological approach, the scientific approach is a conceptual one, using mainly the analysis of specialized literature as well as some practical examples that have the role of emphasizing the interdependence between marketing creativity and the social aspects that it can influence. The general objective pursued in the article is the study of consumer behavior both at the level of influencing factors and at the level of the decision-making process, because marketing stimuli once penetrated into the conscious mind of the consumer determine a series of psychological reactions that generate buying or non-buying behavior .

In carrying out the present study, which is a descriptive one, observation and logical-deductive reasoning were used as tools. As research methods that we used in the study, we list: documentation - through the analysis of specialized literature (especially theoretical documentation); classification and synthesis, but also the method of interdisciplinary research using knowledge from the sphere of psychology, sociology, anthropology, economics, food chemistry and nutrition.

RESULTS

Famine - the paradox of our days, a major social problem - still represents one of the most pressing global threats. The linear economy has encouraged consumption (recently “shopping” is seen as a way to relax and not a necessity), ignoring the finite nature of resources. This trend can only be changed by educating and making people aware of the consequences of their actions and the benefits of redistributing, recycling or donating products, guided by the principles of ethical consumption.

Stenmarck and colleagues (2016) identified the potential generating factors of food waste and divided them into behavioral factors, personal factors, factors related to the food product itself and factors from a social perspective.

Behavioral factors

- inefficient procurement planning and organization practices;
- inefficient establishment of menus;
- purchasing quantities larger than necessary;
- impulsive purchases;
- greater frequency of purchases;
- defective food storage;

- overestimation of the consumption of a certain food;
- misinterpretation of the information on the product label.

Personal factors:

- food habits and preferences;
- not mastering the art of cooking;
- individual responsibility regarding food waste;
- level of education and income;
- availability of time allocated to meal preparation;

Factors related to the food product:

- organoleptic properties of food products;
- perishability of food products;
- improper packaging of food products;

Factors from a social perspective:

- economic factors (increase in the quantity purchased due to the reduction in prices);
- socio-cultural factors (education and support of consumerism);
- climatic factors (waste of fresh food products during the summer, due to the temperature).

Consumerism (producing more than consuming) has encompassed developed countries like an octopus and this phenomenon involves enormous environmental and resource costs. From this point of view, research related to consumer behavior is particularly important in a consumer society (Vida 2023), because an educated consumer will be much more rigorous with his choices.

The analysis of consumer behavior is a multidisciplinary action assuming knowledge from economics, nutrition, sociology, psychology and food chemistry.

Interdisciplinarity answers the following questions:

- what is the reason we buy food?
- why do we prefer some foods over others?
- what pathology is behind an unhealthy eating behavior?
- what would lead us to change certain eating habits?
- to what extent does eating behavior contribute to improving well-being?

Preventing food waste can only be achieved through a joint global effort, requiring consumer involvement, political will, propaganda, but also an understanding of public policy tools.

Involving society and the people can also be achieved through social marketing. It proves to be extremely useful in efforts to promote social causes, in our case the reduction of food waste through rational and sustainable consumption.

Marketing, in all its dimension, requires the study of consumer behavior both at the level of influencing factors and at the level of the decision-making process because marketing stimuli, once penetrated into the conscious mind of the consumer, determine a series of psychological reactions that generate buying or non-buying behavior.

Social marketing appeared in the 1970s, when Philip Kotler and Gerald Zaltman extrapolated the principles of classical marketing used to sell products and services and on the induction of ideas, attitudes and behaviors (Canja et al. 2014). Later, this concept was also used by the World Bank and the World Health Organization.

Thus, the goal of social marketing is to channel efforts to influence behaviors in a benevolent way, and this will bring benefits especially in the sphere of health and the environment (Savciuc 2016) generating social profit.

Social marketing techniques are used to disseminate messages to different target groups. These messages aim to raise awareness of a specific behavior and are tailored to the characteristics of the target group (age, socio-economic status). The ultimate objective of the social marketing message is to mobilize, empower or inform the target audience. The messages are generally simple and are supported by brochures, newsletters or symposia.

In addition to awareness raising, education plays a key role in the prevention of food waste (Fig. 2). In practice, it is education that makes people aware of the problems, and this leads to a change in mentality, attitude and behavior, generating empowerment.

Fig. 2. Generating empowerment through education. Source: authors

Implementing measures to reduce food waste requires an integrated approach at all stages of the food chain (from production to consumption). Initially, measures to reduce food waste can be overwhelming, but in the long term, once routine, these small individual actions, without a major impact at the beginning, prove to be extremely effective in the medium and long term, turning into healthy habits for the consumer and the environment.

Aware of the benefits of social marketing in shaping consumer behavior, more and more countries have created impactful messaging to reduce food waste (Moise 2023):

- Spain: „*Mas alimento, menos desperdicio*” / „*More food, less waste*”
- Denmark: „*Stop Spild Af Mad*” / „*Stop Wasting Food*”
- Germany: „*Lebensmittel wertschätzen*” / „*Value Food*”
- Belgium: „*Good Food*”
- Netherlands: „*Samen tegen Voedselverspilling*” / „*Together against food waste*”
- United Kingdom: „*Love Food, Hate Waste*”

When a consumer perceives a product as valuable, he tends to take better care of it, thus increasing its durability. In the food industry, this principle can be put into practice by

creatively capitalizing on expired foods, by obtaining a new finished product that complies with quality standards and does not endanger the health of the consumer.

Over time, the principles of social marketing (Cheng 2011) have proven their effectiveness in several areas (Canja 2014; Gorgan 2022):

- health promotion (reduction of alcohol and tobacco use and prevention of obesity);
- avoiding incidents (use of seat belt)
- environmental protection (reducing food waste and implicitly waste, protecting the wild habitat);
- civic action (donating blood, voting).

Applying the principles of social marketing in the public sphere represents a real challenge. The success of social marketing campaigns is achieved when the benefits that the consumer obtains through behavior modeling are tangible.

What differentiates commercial marketing from social marketing is the directing of effort by the stakeholders. In the first case, the effort is channeled towards the promotion of goods and services, while in social marketing the effort is directed towards influencing the behavior of the target segment to accept new habits: sorting waste, banning smoking in public spaces, supporting regular physical effort, donating.

Behavioral changes (MacFadyen 1999) can manifest themselves in the short or long term, they can occur at the individual, group or society level (Savciuc 2016). (Table 1).

Table 1: The 6 types of social change that can be induced through social marketing.

	Individual change	Change at group level	Change at the society level
Short-term change	Changing the person`s behavior (giving up compulsive buying)	Administrative changes (Applying the principles (First In - First Out/First Expired - First Out))	Changes of public policies (Laws on reducing food waste: L49/2024, L 217/2016)
Long-term chang	Lifestyle change (setting certain days for supply and buying on a list)	Organizational changes (the use of recyclable packaging, the selective waste collection)	“Socio-economic-cultural evolution” (reducing the negative effects of consumerism)

Source: Adapted from MacFadyen, Stead, Hastings

An aspect that must be taken into account when using social marketing techniques is represented by the fact that behavior change is carried out voluntarily and the only chance to be successful with the campaigns carried out is to reach a certain level of empathy from the target segment in the context in which the community understood the advantages obtained as a result of the behavior change.

DISCUSSION

Due to the complexity of social marketing by inducing messages that aim to change behavior, its approach needs to be as creative as possible, requiring a holistic vision in creating memorable messages and advertising images. In order to ensure that the message

is best assimilated by the target audience, it is recommended that social marketing takes into account sensory marketing techniques.

Sensory marketing is a relatively new advertising technique that relies on the use of the five human senses (sight, hearing, smell, taste and touch) in order to create an emotional association with a particular product, brand or message, because people as consumers they react to their emotional impulses more than to their rational impulses. The purpose of this type of marketing is to provide satisfaction to the consumer through sensory stimulation. To achieve a sensory impact, the SPC (stimulus, process and consequence) model is established, taking into account the fact that when several senses are stimulated at once, they amplify each other. In any case, it is essential to remember that more than 90% of all information received is processed at a subconscious level in the brain (Zurawicki 2010).

When analyzing the consumer behavior in Romania, it is necessary to take into account the mark that the communist period has left on generations, characterized by food deprivation, but also by a false “well-being” that generally offered a feeling of sufficiency without the need for additional effort to get out from the comfort zone. “Rational” nutrition, which claimed to be based on scientific analysis, was nothing more than a policy of dietary restraint. Communism was a period of cards and queues, and the 1980s were the peak of food shortages: queues for bread, eggs, milk, oil and sugar, etc., i.e. for the food necessary for daily survival (Nicoară 2006).

With the end of the communist era, the consumer, marked by the pressure of rationing, has increasingly poorly managed access to food, sliding down the slope of consumerism and food waste, which has manifested itself in the food industry, the hospitality industry, the agro-zootechnical sector, etc. Today we live in a world where consumerism has successfully crept in. Driven by the temptation of hedonism, we have become a society addicted to pleasure consumption, purchasing far in excess of real needs. Today we buy things to fulfill our bodily, emotional, sensory, aesthetic, relational, relational, sanitary, playful and entertaining needs. We want the things we buy to give us pleasure, to improve our quality of life, to maintain or improve our health and, if possible, to preserve our youth. We tread on quicksand, deluding ourselves that all this will bring us a sense of achievement.

The psychophysiological characteristics that generate consumption behavior are based on mechanically repeated actions (Mateescu 2022). For this reason, a series of simple measures can be taken to limit the impulse to overbuy:

- meal planning;
- drawing up a shopping list adapted to daily needs;
- avoiding buying discounted products for large quantities;
- paying attention to unsealed products in the fridge;
- using stored vegetables and fruit in recipes;
- freezing portions of food if overcooking.

In the rush for profit, economic agents have promoted the positive side of consumerism, because consumer spending is the key for the economy development, so, increasing consumption of goods and services is seen as an economically favorable act.

Even if it is vital to modern history (consumption is seen as a driving force of the world economy), its scale can be adjusted so that it no longer has negative effects on the

environment and this can only be done in line with the principles of sustainable development.

Regarding future research directions, they must also take into account major changes generated by the crisis felt as a result of the Ukraine war, but also by the economic instability that is manifested both at the national and international levels, aspects that can bring major changes in consumer behavior.

CONCLUSIONS

Although it is an overwhelming problem, there are ways to both prevent and reduce food waste. The adage “a little goes a long way” is very applicable and in this case, small changes at the individual level can make a big difference to the amount of food wastage.

What can be achieved with the help of social marketing is the awareness of the consumer that he can make correct choices both for himself and for the environment and through repetition, these choices can turn into a lifestyle. From this point of view, social marketing proves to be extremely useful in making efforts to promote some social causes, in our case the reduction of food waste through rational and sustainable consumption.

Last but not least, we want to emphasize that, on a small scale, a circular economy model in which the phenomenon of food waste is small, we find it within the small household in the mountain area, where people produce for their own consumption, and most of leftovers are taken into the animal circuit or turned into compost. This model, as well as the role of social marketing in its promotion, will be the future direction of research that will be the subject of a new article.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This article is realized in the framework of the ADER 17.1.1/2024 project entitled *Research on the evolution of food waste at national level, from the perspective of Romania's commitment to achieve the Sustainable Development Goal, Phase II called Analysis of the current state of food waste in 2024.*

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, AM și SI. Formal analysis, AM. Research, AM. Drafting - original draft, AM. Writing - revising and editing AM, SI, CBC.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD STATEMENT

Not applicable.

INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

Not applicable.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data supporting the results of this study are available in the article

REFERENCES

- Adelodun B, Kareem KY, Kumar P, Kumar V, Choi KS, Yadav KK, Yadav A, El-Denglawey A, Cabral-Pinto M, Son CT, Krishnan S, Khan NA.** 2021. *Understanding the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on sustainable agri-food system and agroecosystem decarbonization nexus: A review.* Journal of Cleaner Production, [ejournal] 318, pp.1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128451>.
- Amicarelli V, Lagioia G, Bux C.** 2021. Global warming potential of food waste through the life cycle assessment: An analytical review. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 91, nr. articol 106677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2021.106677>.
- Antonescu D, Surdu I, Apetrei M.** 2023. *Theoretical and practical aspects regarding food waste in Romania and in a global context.* Cluj University Press.
- Canja A, Railean A, Carmanovic I.** 2014. Social marketing - essence, principles, usefulness. Technical-UTM, 2014, Vol.3, pp. 419-422. ISBN 978-9975-45-249-6.
- Chauhan C, Dhir A, Akram MU, Salo, J.** 2021. Food loss and waste in food supply chains. A systematic literature review and framework development approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126438>.
- Cheng H, Kotler Ph, Lee N R.** Social marketing for public health: global trends and success stories, USA: Jones and Bartlett Publishers, 2011, 422 p. ISBN 978-0763757977.
- Djekic I, Battle-Bayer L, Bala A, Fullana-I-palmer P and Jambrak AR.** 2021. Role of the Food Supply Chain Stakeholders in Achieving UN SDGs. *Sustainability*, [e-journal] 3(16), pp.1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169095>.
- Do Q, Ramudhin A, Colicchia C, Creazza A, Li D.** 2021. A Systematic Review of Research on Food Loss and Waste Prevention and Management for the Circular Economy. *International Journal of Production Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2021.108209>.
- European Commission,** 2019. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. The European Green Deal, Brussels. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52019DC0640&from=EN>, accessed on 28.09.2024.
- European Parliament,** 2011. Report on how to avoid food wastage: strategies for a more efficient food chain in the EU. Available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-7-2011-0430_EN.pdf, accessed on 19.09.2024.
- Evans D.** 2011. Beyond the throwaway society: Ordinary domestic practice and a sociological approach to household food waste. *Sociology*, 46(1), pp. 41-56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038511416150>.
- FAO,** 2011. Global food losses and food waste – Extent, causes and prevention. Rome. Disponibil online la adresa: <http://www.fao.org/3/mb060e/mb060e00>, accessed on 05.08.2024.
- Giroto F, Alibardi L, Cossu R.** 2015. Food waste generation and industrial uses: A review. *Waste Management*, 45, pp. 32–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2015.06.008>.
- Gkountani VA, Tsoulfas GT.** 2021. Circular economy and food production systems: tracing linkages and exploring synergies. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 21(2), pp.281–288.

- Gorgan C, Chersan IC, Dragomir VD, Dumitru M.** 2022. Food Waste Prevention Solutions in the Annual Reports of European Companies. *Amfiteatru Economic*, 24(60), pp. 309-329.
- MacFadyen L, Stead L, Hastings M.** 1999. *Synopsis of Social Marketing*, Glasgow: University of Strathclyde, 1999.
- Mateescu O.** 2022. Economic Psychology. University course, "Titu Maiorescu" University, p.32, [online]. disponibil:<http://documents.tips/documents/psihologie-economica.html>;
- Moise RE.** 2023. Food waste - consumer challenges in reducing food waste. Dissertation. University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Bucharest.
- Nicoară M T.** 2006. No appetite for black roe and goose livers! Food - ideological instrument of Romanian communism! *Notebooks of Historical Anthropology* 8-9:309-317.
- Ocicka B, Raźniewska M.** 2018. Food waste reduction as a challenge in supply chains management. *LogForum*, [e-journal] 14(4), pp.549-561. DOI: 10.17270/J.LOG.2018.303.
- Priefer, C, Jörissen J, Bräutigam KR.** 2016. Food waste prevention in Europe—A cause driven approach to identify the most relevant leverage points for action. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 109, pp. 155-165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.03.004>.
- Rey R.** 1979. Mountain economy and rentability. *Flacăra Magazine*, No. 27.
- Savciuc O.** 2016. Application of social marketing in public health. Chisinau, Republic of Moldova: Editorial-Poligrafic Department of ASEM, 2016, Vol.2, pp. 217-223. ISBN 978-9975-75-835-2.
- Schinkel J.** 2019. Review of policy instruments and recommendations for effective food waste prevention. *Proceedings of Institution of Civil Engineers: Waste and Resource Management*, [e-journal] 172(3), pp.92-101. <https://doi.org/10.1680/jwarm.18.00022>.
- Stenmarck A, Jensen C, Quedsted T, Moates G, Buksti M, Cseh B, Juul S, Parry A, Politano A, Redlingshofer B, Scherhauser S, Silvennoinen K, Soethoudt J M, Zübert C, Östergren K.** 2016. Estimates of European food waste levels. *IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute*, <https://edepot.wur.nl/378674>.
- United Nations Environment Programme**, 2021. *UNEP Food Waste Index Report 2021*.
- United Nations**, 2015. *Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*.
- Vida G.** 2023. *The environmental attitude of the consumer towards food*. DOI: 10.46727/c.v2.18-19-03-2023. p. 51-54.
- Zurawicki L.** 2010. *Neuromarketing: exploring the brain of the consumer*. Berlin: Springer.